

SELF-HEALING OF EPOXY RESINS USING SELF ASSEMBLING HEALING AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

We describe the concept of self-assembly through ionomer formation to achieve healing agents of critical molecular weight (MW). Thermal self-healing of epoxy resins could be induced while maintaining a low resin blend viscosity for direct fibre impregnation. DGEBA with a 'relatively low' MW was end-capped with 4-amino salicylic acid sodium salt to introduce ionomer functionality for self-assembly. Healing efficiencies were comparable to those obtained with 'high' MW linear epoxy and Phenoxy polymers of similar molecular structure. The non-reactive end capped DGEBA monomers, which cannot self-assembly had limited ability to heal thermoset epoxy resins used for industrial and aerospace applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are used as matrices for composite materials. Matrix resins need to be made self-mendable in order to prolong the life of composite structures. The incorporation of microcapsules of healing agents (HA) and curing agents and/or dispersed catalysts is reported to provide healing capability (1). However, Hayes et al. [2-4] showed that a soluble linear polymer could introduce a self-healing function to epoxy resins. The linear polymer diffuses to the crack faces when the temperature exceeds the onset of the glass transition region to enable thermal mending. The most effective HA had an average MW of 44,000 g/mol but this increased the viscosity of the liquid epoxy resin limiting the rate of impregnation of the fibres during manufacture of a composite artefact. Jamil et al. [5,6] employed end-capped low MW epoxies in a study of the diffusion mechanism for healing. The MW of HA was found to be critical for healing efficiency because effective healing was inhibited significantly by phase separation of the HA.

In this study we explored the self-assembly of ionomer end-capped low MW epoxies as a mechanism for dealing with the 'high' viscosity of the healable resin for impregnation of the fibres. The healing efficiency of these cured resins was quantified using the recovery of single-edge notch strength.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Matrix Resins

Matrix 1 was an epoxy, which consisted of 36.9 % w/w TGAP (triglycidyl p-amino phenol-MY 0510), 35.4 % w/w DGEBF (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F -GY 281 (EEW = 159-172)) and cured with 27.7 % w/w DDS (4,4'-diamino diphenyl sulphone). The recipe was chosen to simulate a high temperature

performing resin required for aerospace applications. The resin mixture was degassed at 145°C for 45 mins under vacuum before casting in ‘PTFE’ coated metal SEN moulds for curing for 3h at 180°C. The samples were cooled down in the oven over 2 hours at 2°C per min. Figure 1 gives the structures of the DGEBA epoxy resin and amine hardener for Matrix 2. Matrix 2 was an industrial epoxy consisting of DGEBA (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A-Fig.1a with $n \approx 0.17$) – DER 331 (Dow, Australia). The hardener was diethyl toluene diamine (DETDA) -Ethacure 100 (Chemtura, Australia). The resin blend was degassed in a rotary evaporator at 95°C and cast into silicone rubber moulds for curing at 150°C for 10 hours.

2.2 Healing agents

Figure 1 also gives the structures of DGEBA epoxy resins and the linear Phenoxy polymer. The original healing agent, which was used as a reference, was a linear DGEBA type polymer (Figure 1a with $n \approx 130$) with viscosity average molecular weight of 44,000 g mol⁻¹ without reactive glycidyl end-groups (Sigma-Aldrich). Two commercial Phenoxy polymers (InChem Corp.USA) with similar chemical structure and which do not have glycidyl end-groups were also used: PKHP-200 ($M_n = 10,000$, $M_w = 32,000$ g mol⁻¹) and PKFE ($M_n = 16,000$, $M_w = 60,000$ g mol⁻¹).

Two low molecular weight healing agents were prepared from diglycidyl bisphenol A-co-epichlorohydrin (DGEBA 4000 and DGEBA 6100 -Figure 1a with average values of $n \approx 11.8$, 18) (Sigma -Aldrich). They were end-capped by reaction with benzoic acid (End Cap 1-3), isophthalic acid or 4-amino salicylic acid sodium salt (Na DGEBA (4000) and (Na DGEBA (6100)/ PolyBis Na)). The latter two provided the HA with ionomer characteristics.

The reference HA was a DGEBA linear polymer without glycidyl end-groups similar in structure to Figure 1a. The reported MW of 44,000 infers that the average value of $n \approx 130$. The HAs were dissolved in the epoxy resin blends in the absence of the hardener at temperatures up to 130°C. The concentration of HA employed was 7.5% as identified elsewhere [2-4]. The end-capped low M_n DGEBA 4000 and 6100 g mol⁻¹ were used at concentrations of 7.0%.

2.3 Healing Assessment

Healing was evaluated using the single end notched beam (SENB) test. Samples were prepared according to ASTM D5045. While the specimen was supported in a jig, a pre-crack was introduced using a light tap with a hammer on a razor blade supported in the notch. The load to fracture the specimen in a three-point bend fixture with a span of 35 mm was recorded. The fractured specimens were healed in a jig, which was designed to maintain intimate and aligned contact between the crack surfaces. Figure 2 shows the jig employed.

The Tg of Matrix 1 was found to be 200°C. Therefore healing of Matrix 1 was undertaken at that temperature of 200°C over 3 hours in a preheated oven, with cooling within the oven. The healing efficiency is an average of the percentage recovery of the load to fracture of the virgin coupon. 18 specimens were tested in most cases. Specimens with clear evidence of misalignment after healing were not included in the analysis. Figure 3 is a photograph of a healed coupon from DEGEBA 44,000 self-healable (SH) Matrix 1. The memory of the original fracture can be observed by careful inspection.

Figure 1: Structures of the components of Matrix 2 and Healing Agents: a) DGEBA Epoxy resin - glycidyl end-capped poly(bisphenol A-co-epichlorohydrin) where $n \approx 0.17$; b) Matrix 2 hardener- diethyl toluene diamine (DTEDA); c) phenoxy polymer; d) isophthalic end-capped poly(bisphenol A-co-epichlorohydrin) ($M_n = 6100$); e) sodium salicylate end-capped poly(bisphenol A-co-epichlorohydrin) ($M_n = 6100$ and 4000).

Figure 2: Alignment jig for thermal healing.

Figure 3: Example of a thermally healed SENB coupon from Matrix 1 showing a healed crack.

The T_g of the unmodified resin used as Matrix 2 was 168°C. In this case, healing was undertaken at a temperature of 185°C over 2 hours. Near IR spectroscopy could not detect additional cure during healing [6]. The healing efficiency was determined from the recovery in the load to fracture and no attempt to determine fracture toughness was made because the crack length after healing cannot be determined, as discussed by Brown [7].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Matrix 1

3.1.1 Linear Healing Agents

Fig.4 shows the efficiency of healing achieved using linear polymers of relatively high MW HA in Matrix 1. Up to 8 healing cycles at 200°C were employed before the experiments were interrupted mainly because a plateau in healing efficiency had occurred. The healing is reported as a fraction of the original SENB load to fracture. For each system the results are the average of ≈ 18 tests. Occasionally misalignment of the crack faces occurred in the jig during healing and these specimens were omitted from the analysis. The healing efficiency of the resin containing the Phenoxy HAs was particularly interesting: PKHP 200 provided a plateau in healing efficiency at $\approx 40\%$ after 8 healing events. Matrix containing PKFE continued to be healable at $\approx 30\%$. The reasons for this difference are unclear but we note that Phenoxy PKHP 200 has $M_n = 10,000$ and $M_w = 32,000$ g mol⁻¹ and Phenoxy PKFE has $M_n = 16,000$ and $M_w = 60,000$ g mol⁻¹. We can postulate that the lower MW of the Phenoxy PKHP means that the rate of diffusion of the linear polymer to the crack tip is higher to provide more efficient healing.

Figure 4: Healing efficiencies of Matrix 1 containing 7.5 % of three 'linear epoxy' polymers; DGEBA1 = DGEBA 44,000; Phenoxy PHP200; Phenoxy PKFE. The control is the unmodified resin.

The HA used in the 'original' research [1] DGEBA 1 (Figure 4) and 2 (Figure 5) also behaved similarly to Phenoxy PKFE, with an apparent plateau in healing efficiency of $\approx 30\%$. DGEBA1 and DGEBA 2 refer to two separate experiments. In previous work [4,5] we demonstrated that phase

separation of the HA is responsible for the reduction in healing efficiency above a 7.5% loading. The Phenoxies and DGEBA 44,000 have nominally identical molecular structures with only differences in molecular chain length and distribution. Therefore an alternative explanation could involve partial phase separation of Phenoxy PKFE during the first healing cycles since epoxy resins tend to become denser through post-curing and/or equilibration of the network [8]. Reaction induced phase separation is well known chemistry for designing toughened epoxies. Compared to the non-healable control, the 'healability' declines similarly over the first 3 healing cycles, which shows that the structure of the epoxy network is changing.

Two low MW HAs (DGEBA 4000 and DGEBA 6100) (Figure 1a with $n = 11.8, 18$ respectively) were end-capped with benzoic acid to remove the epoxy reactivity. Figure 5 shows that they introduced only marginal improvements in healing efficiency relative to the control, without dissolved HA. Healing has two components involving diffusion of the HA and a small degree of post-curing, which arises from the equilibration of the network. These results demonstrate that the MW of the HA is a critical parameter whose value reflects the lowest MW for rapid diffusion and the MW required for entanglement with the network. The contributions of the reptation of linear polymer to crack surfaces and the development of entanglements to healing in thermosets have been discussed recently [9].

3.1.2 Self Assembling Healing Agents

From the above analysis it becomes clear that the requirements in MW for an optimum HA tend to be in opposition: A low MW is required for rapid diffusional healing but high MW for stable crack closing through molecular entanglement. Self-assembling of a low MW polymer into a HA provides a mechanism of achieving these criteria. Thus an ionomer provides a mechanism for reversible assembly of a 'low' MW HA, which combines rapid diffusional healing with efficient of crack closure for optimized healing efficiency. At the same time the viscosity of the resin does not increase and compromise the composite processing method.

Figure 5: Healing Efficiencies of Matrix 1 containing 7.5 % Na DGEBA (4000) (Na ionomer) in comparison to 7 % non self-assembling end capped low MW HA, 7.5% DEGBA 44,000 (DEGBA2) and the unmodified resin (control). End Cap 1 = DGEBA 6100, End Cap 2 = DGEBA 4000, End Cap 3 = DGEBA 4000.

This hypothesis has been demonstrated by studying the healing efficiency achieved with the Na ionomer system (Na DGEBA (4000)). DGEBA 4000 was end capped with a self-assembling ionomer (Na^+ carboxylate) end-group. This was achieved by reacting the glycidyl groups on DGEBA 4000 with 4-amino-salicylic acid sodium salt, in the melt in vacuum, at 130°C for 5 mins.

Figure 5 shows the healing efficiency of the Matrix 1 containing 7.5 % Na DGEBA (4000) (Na ionomer) over 7 cycles. The healing efficiencies are similar to those for the DGEBA 2 (Figure 5) and with DGEBA 1 and Phenoxy PKFE, in Figure 4. These results support the hypothesis that reversible self-assembly of the HA through ionomer formation occurs in the cured resin. During healing the ionomers dissociate for diffusion to the crack surfaces and self-assemble on cooling. The mechanism was examined further by healing Matrix 2 with a series of related ionomers.

3.2 Matrix 2

The efficacy of the Phenoxy PKHP 200 for thermal healing of Matrix 2 was used to establish that soluble linear polymers are generic in the healing of differing epoxy networks. Fig. 6 shows the recovered load to fracture for a series of healed coupons. We have not calculated the healing efficiency because of the toughness introduced to the system and at these concentrations complicate the interpretation of the data.

Figure 6: Load recovery of Matrix 2 containing various concentrations of Phenoxy PKHP 200 after healing.

For comparison with the data from Matrix 1, we estimate that the unmodified coupon exhibited healing efficiency of 13% in cycle 2 and 2% in cycle 3, which compares well with the control for Matrix 1 (Figure. 4). With 7.5% HA, healing efficiencies of 70% and 40% were observed after similar healing cycles, which compare favourably with those for Matrix 1. It is noticeable that with $>7.5\%$ (10 and 12 %) PKHP 200 the mechanism of healing may have changed for 3rd healing cycle. Meure [10] reported that phase separated thermoplastics can heal cracks by physical transport. Jones and Varley [9] have reviewed these mechanisms recently. Further work on the mechanism is required.

Figure 7: Load recovery after healing for Matrix 2 containing various concentrations of Na DGEBA (6100)-a sodium carboxylate terminated poly (bisphenol A-co-epichlorohydrin)-(PolyBis Na).

Healing Agent	End Cap	Heal 1 (N)	Heal 2 (N)	Heal 3 (N)
None		20.5 ± 3	2.5 ± 2	0.6 ± 0.8
DGEBA 6100	Na 4-amino salicylate	30 ± 3.5	26 ± 3	20 ± 2
DGEBA 6100	Na 4-amino salicylate/isophthalic acid	25 ± 6	22 ± 2	17 ± 2
DGEBA 6100	isophthalic acid	30 ± 5	23 ± 3	18.5 ± 2
DGEBA 4000	Na 4-amino salicylate	28 ± 5	22 ± 5	17 ± 3

Table 1: Load recovery (N) after healing for 2 hours at 185°C of Matrix 2 containing 10% isophthalic end-capped DGEBA 6100, ionomer end-capped DGEBA 4000, 6100 and mixed HA system.

Figure 7 shows the efficiency of healing of Matrix 2 with the ionomer HA. After the first healing cycle, the Na DGEBA (6100) ionomer system exhibited a 40% and 70% increase in healing compared with the unmodified network.

To explore the self-assembly of the carboxyl and carboxylated terminated HAs further experiments with isophthalic acid end-capped HA are reported in Table 1. The isophthalic and mixed sodium carboxylate and isophthalic end-capped DGEBA exhibited similar load recovery to the Na DGEBA (6100) in Fig. 7. These results are consistent with the mechanism of in-situ self-assembly of a linear polymeric healing agent with effective molecular weight. Association of the carboxylic acid groups through hydrogen bonding appears to be able to introduce a self-assembling mechanism, similarly to the ionomer end-capped DGEBA [11]. We conclude that reversible association/self-assembly of ionic healing agents should be explored for healing matrices in composite materials.

4. Conclusions

Linear polymers, which are soluble in both aerospace and industrial epoxy resin-systems, enable them to be made thermally mendable. The critical molecular weight (MW) of the healing agent has been explored using unreactive end capped 'low' MW epoxy monomers of differing degrees of polymerization. Intermediate MW linear epoxy polymers such as the Phenoxies are effective in healing crosslinked thermoset epoxy resin matrices.

The disadvantage of dissolving relatively high MW polymeric healing agents into the epoxy resin prior to composite manufacture is the increase in viscosity. By utilizing the association/dissociation concept of ionomers the effect on viscosity has been minimised. 'Low' MW DGEBA epoxy monomers have been end-capped with Na carboxylate groups, which enabled reversible self-assembly into longer chains for efficient thermal healing. Similar healing efficiencies of the 'ionomer' and long chain Phenoxies support the association hypothesis. In addition, the self-assembly of carboxyl end-capped 'low' MW epoxy HAs and mixed systems have been explored. Further work is required to demonstrate that ionomer characteristics are responsible for the observations and that mendable composites can be manufactured by direct fibre impregnation methods such as RTM.

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6. References

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